

11-16 AUGUST 2019

22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

PREDICTING THE CONSOLIDATION OF FABRIC-REINFORCED STRUCTURAL POWER COMPOSITES

M. Valkova^{1,2*}, E. S. Greenhalgh¹, M. S. P. Shaffer² and D. B. Anthony^{1,2}.

¹ Department of Aeronautics, Imperial College London, UK; ² Department of Chemistry, Imperial College, London, UK
* Corresponding author (maria.valkova13@imperial.ac.uk)

Imperial College London, UK
www.imperial.ac.uk/composites-centre/
August 2019

CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

CONFERENCE
DESTINATION
SUPPORTERS:

The Composites Centre
for research, modelling, testing and training in advanced composites

**Imperial College
London**

#ICCM22

Introduction

- The goal of structural power composites (SPCs) research is to achieve competitive energy and power densities while maintaining structural integrity.
- Most of the successfully demonstrated SPC devices employ a laminated construction^[1,2], combining woven fabric reinforcements (WFR) in a hybrid layup.
- Optimal consolidation of the reinforcements is key for both mechanical and electrochemical performance of SPCs.

Motivation for current work

- 1)
 - Reinforcement choice and/or surface modifications determine layup consolidation properties^[3], and hence, the attainable fibre volume fraction (FVF), and micro- and meso- structure.
 - Expect strong link between structure and SPC properties, as is the case for conventional composites^[4].
 - Ability to predict structure and properties will aid selection of reinforcements and processing specifications.
- 2)
 - Need for predictive modelling to assist multifunctional device design and optimisation^[5].
 - Mechanical and electrochemical FEA relies on realistic geometric models as starting point^[4].
 - Generation of accurate geometric models of WFRCs often involves a process modelling step.

Materials

Electrode: Chomarac C-WEAVE™ 200P 3K HS (C)

Separator: Gividi Fabrics srl 1086 (G)

Layups tested	Monolayer	C , G
	Multilayer monolithic	C ₂ , G ₂
	Multilayer hybrid	CG , CGC

Experimental setup

Modelling methodology

- Each fabric modelled as a meso-scale unit cell (UC).
- Average geometric parameters determined from optical microscopy.
- Yarns idealised as continuous, transversely-isotropic, with homogenised properties.
- Fabric compression response is highly non-linear^[6].
- FE sensitivity studies established that the transverse modulus of yarns (E_2) governs this response.

Modelling methodology

- Assumed bi-exponential evolution of E_2 with local FVF($V_{f,l}$): $E_2 = a \exp(b V_{f,l}) + c \exp(d V_{f,l})$
- $V_{f,l}$ calculated based on the element volume change, represented by the Jacobian (J):
$$V_{f,l} = V_{f,l,0} / J \quad \text{and} \quad J = \det(F)$$
where F is the deformation gradient and $V_{f,l,0}$ is the undisturbed FVF.
- Material nonlinearity implemented through a user subroutine (VUMAT).
- Monolayer models calibrated against measured compression responses.

Modelling methodology

- Inter-ply nesting is a typical feature of fabric reinforced composites.
- Range of potential nesting configurations in multilayer fabric stacks, resulting in range of architectures.
- Limiting cases of minimum and maximum nesting of adjacent layers considered:
 - in-phase (IP)
 - 90° out-of-phase (OP)

 $G_{2,OP}$

Modelling methodology

- Dissimilar UC size of C and G implies that tessellation required to construct a multilayer hybrid unit cell (hUC).
- To minimise computational domain while preserving periodicity, hUCs constructed using approximate fabric geometric parameters within measurement uncertainty, allowing a 1:5 tessellation ratio.
- Limiting cases of nesting considered for CGC (device) stack.

Results

- Monolithic multilayer results indicate OP stacking results in greater structural homogeneity and higher FVF than IP.
- Difference between IP and OP model compaction responses greater than experimentally measured range, indicating only moderate nesting achieved in practice. Ply misalignment, shear and variability as possible causes.

Local Fibre
Volume Fraction

Results

- IP vs. OP Hybrid multilayer model results suggest nesting of outer layers may still be transmitted through separator.
- In practice, experimental consolidation range displays only moderate inter-ply nesting.

Local Fibre
Volume Fraction

CGC_{IP}

CGC_{OP}

Results

- IP vs. OP Hybrid multilayer model results suggest nesting of outer layers may still be transmitted through separator.
- In practice, experimental consolidation range displays only moderate inter-ply nesting. Findings supported by optical microscopy:

35° phase shift in C layers.

Results

- Fibre surface modifications frequently pursued as means to increase electrode surface area – in this case carbon aerogel (CAG).
- CAG-modified carbon fibre fabric (C*) and device layup (C*GC*) display marked decrease in compressibility in transverse compaction tests.

Conclusions

- Attainable FVF in SPCs dependent on selection of reinforcements and/or presence of surface modifications; additional limitations due to ply variability, handling and layup process.
- Procedure for generation of meso-FE models of WFR SPCs established. Exact prediction of WFR SPC architecture challenging due to inherent process variability.
- 3D models of device meso-architecture to be used in further mechanical and electrochemical FEA.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to acknowledge the funding provided by the EPSRC Future Composites Research Manufacturing Hub (EP/P006701/1), the EPSRC Beyond Structural project (EP/P007465/1), the European Office of Aerospace Research and Development (IOE Grant FA9550-17-1-0251) and EU Clean Sky 2 (SORCERER Project #738085).